

Higher Education for Women in India: Achievements and Challenges

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Abstract

Education is the yardstick by which the growth and development of a country. This paper constitutes the importance of higher education in socio-economic growth of women in a society. It also ascertain the success and challenges in the attainment of higher education by a women in India and how much the intellectual growth has up lift the society. Women education always been a concerning issues for Indian government as educated women plays a pivotal role in the development of a society as well as the country. In this paper also mention the necessary and factors responsible for women participation in higher education. This paper also discussed government programs for improving women education and finally it gives some suggestions which can accelerate women participation in higher education in India.

"If you educate a man, you educate an individual. But if you educate women, you educate a nation"

Introduction

Higher education means the education beyond the level of secondary education. It is often assumed that education imparted by the colleges or universities are higher education. But in fact higher educational institutions include Professional Schools in the field of Law, Theology, Medicine, Business, Music and Art. It also includes other institutions like Teachers Training School and Technological Institutions. Moreover, institutions for training of highly skilled specialists in the field of economics, science, technology and culture of various types of higher schools are treated as Higher Educational Institutions. Because these institutions allow those candidates in their campus who have completed their study at the secondary level. Thus in general the term „Higher Education refers the education at the degree level and above.

Women Education in Different Periods

Women's Education in Ancient India:- Since from the ancient time women had obsessed a bit lower position then men in the society due to the set of rigid social norms. But during Vedic periods their position was much better and they used to right of entry the higher

education but with the course of time she lost her importance. Women education in ancient India prevailed during the early Vedic period. Most of the Indian scriptures Rig Veda and Upanishads mention about several women sages and seers. However after 500 B.C, the position of women started to decline. But the Islamic invasion had restricted the freedom and rights of women.

Women's Education in Medieval India:- during medieval India after the introduction of Purdah system the condition of women education further deteriorated. Different religious (Hinduism , Islamic ,Christianity) conventions and customs had deteriorate her status further. Education in medieval India flourished during the Mughal rule from 1546-1848 where education system was under Ulama where education meant religious training of a variety of subjects like medicine, Arabic literature, philosophy, grammar, history, law, administration and ethics. A sequences of socio- religious movements contributed to the development of women's education in the country. Many rulers like Iltutmish, Akbar etc. took several initiatives to make education available to the women of India. The ordered form of women education in India was incorporated in the early centuries of the Christian era.

Women's Education in Colonial India: - During the colonial era in India there was a revival of interest in women's education again. Various eminent leaders like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar had given special emphasized on the education of women. However on the other side Mahatma Jyotiba Phule, Periyar and Baba Saheb Ambedkar were those eminent leaders who worked for the upliftment and attainment of education for women of the lower castes. During the colonial period the institutional form of imparting learning was introduced in which women's education had witnessed an essential expansion. Then after various movements were launched to educate country's women. Furthermore, this journey progressed through the years and structured the modern Indian education system.

Women's education in modern India:-after the independence of India in 1947 the women education got a fillip. After independence government has taken various measures for providing education to Indian women. Women literacy rate apparently rose in the modern days. Women education in India became a compulsory concern and female literacy has gone higher than male literacy. As a result of the various government measures undertake during the three decades the growth of female literacy rate was more than male which was about 14.87% as compared to 11.72 % of that of male. While women literacy rate was 22% in 1971 which roused to 54.16% in 2001.

Importance of Higher Education for Women

Almost half of the population in India is occupied by women. They are the half of the human resources. But it is very unfortunate to say that for long years there have been a strong bias against women and thereby there is a tendency to deny equal socio-economic opportunity for them. This neglect attitude towards women is famous in many respects particularly in the field of education. None can deny the fact that education is the fundamental agents for the socio-economic development of a country. But women access in the domain of education has not been fairly treated.

There are two different views on the question of women participation in higher education - traditional and modern. The traditional view supports women's education to equip them to become better wives and mother. This view believes that women's present education is entirely irrelevant in their lives. It is only waste of time and this does not help them to solve the problems of their daily life. This view believe that modern educated women are neither happy nor contended nor socially useful. She is misfit in life and needs opportunities for self expression. But modern attitude visualize education as an instrument for women's equality and development

Theoretically the need of higher education for both males and females is the same. But practically it could be said that female education is more important than that of male. In this connection I may

refer a statement of philosopher-president and noted educationist Dr. S. Radhakrishnan (1948). He says “there cannot be educated people without educated women. If general education has to be limited to men or women, the opportunity should be given to women. From them it would most surely be passed on to the next age group.

Women education has two aspects- individual aspect and social aspect. It is education which increases women’s abilities to deal with the problems of her life, her family, her society and nation. Education increases confidence in a woman. An educated woman can easily appreciate the demerits of early marriage and high birth rate. They have the approach of gender parity among their children right from health care, nutrition, education and even career. The fruits of education are enjoyed not only by the woman worried but it passes to her family in later life. In a word, over all development of a society depends on the development of its total members. But if half of its members are legged behind, obviously it will create hindrance to the development.

Indian Context- Policies and Programmes for Women Higher Education

In India, providing education to all the citizens is a constitutional commitment. The principal of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian constitution, in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. The Constitution not only guarantees equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favor of women. Just after Independence, in 1951, literacy levels were very low (25% for men and 9% for women), In the next ten years there was not much progress in the literacy levels. It is only after the recommendation of the Indian education commission (1964) and the National policy of education (1968) that the education of girls was seen as a means of accelerating social transformation. The policy placed special emphasis on initiating programmes to give equal educational opportunity to all the groups and both sexes. The constitution also gave primary responsibility for elementary education to the state governments, while the central government was given responsibility for technical and higher education. This circumstances changed in 1976 after the 42nd Amendment to the constitution was passed, making all education the joint responsibility of the central and state governments. One of the penalties of this was that the foreign assistance, so far restricted to technical and higher education, now began to flow into primary education as well. Between the mid-1960 and the early 1980s, the proportion of resources going into elementary education showed a steady increase

National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986 and its Programme of Action (POA) gave high priority to gender equality and committed the entire educational system to work for women’s empowerment. The National Perspective Plan 1988-2000 reiterates this point of view and states that women themselves must defeat their handicaps. Thus, there has been a careful articulation of education for equality for women, which is reflected in the educational policy discourse. Central and State governments attached lot of significance to actually operational the NPE’s Programme of Action and in a series of regional meetings with the State Governments, a special review of gender issues in education was undertaken. At the same time it was emphasized to the States, that gender concerns must be built into all educational processes. Monitoring committees for women’s/ girls’ education at the Ministry of Human Resource Development level and also state level were formed to monitor the indicators of gender concerns in all policies and projects. Emphasis was laid on enrolment and retention of the girl child in formal and non formal schooling; staffing of rural women teachers and removal of gender bias in the curriculum.

Mass literacy campaigns in different parts of India were launched which brought out volunteers from all sections of society as instructors, master trainers and organizers. Adult Education Programmes, Total Literacy Campaigns, Post Literacy Programmes, and continuing Education

Programmes were also started. Nation wide gender sensitization programmes were undertaken to cover a large number of educational personnel to include educational administrators, teachers and teacher educators. Complementary to this strategy, media campaigns and parental awareness programmes for generating a positive climate for girls' education were also started. Mobilization of women's groups and projects like Mahila Samakhyas (Education for Women's Equality) with focus on the constraints that had so far banned women and girls from accessing educational inputs were launched. The purpose of these groups was to address issues of self image and self self-assurance of women and alter societal perception about them. Its overall goal was to create circumstances to enable women to better understand their predicament, to move from a state of abject disempowerment towards a situation in which they could decide their own lives and influence their environment, and at the same time create for themselves and their family an educational opportunity which improved the process of development.

Recent Trends in Women Higher Education

In recent times there has been a change in the aspiration of young persons. Both men and women are in a hurry to finish studies and start earning. Money making has become the most important value for them. For this reason, they prefer to take up courses which are linked to jobs and pursue studies for academic purposes are no longer the aim. The rebellion in values cuts across strata, i.e. young persons even from the upper and middle strata want to earn as early as possible. The daughters of city based professional parents have really undergone a sea change in their socialization. Parents are giving the best education to their daughters and expect them to be independent and follow careers. This rebellion in values contrasts with those values which dominated prior to the nineties, i.e. education and its linkage to the job market early on in life was only for those men who needed jobs and was certainly not for women. In this changed situation, the priorities of women have also changed. They too want professional education and are, therefore, entering the so called masculine disciplines.

There are two concurrent trends of clustering and dispersal that can be seen in the participation of men and women in higher education. During the first three decades while women tended to be cluster in the general disciplines of arts and sciences (nearly 90 percent); men's participation was characterized by both clustering in arts and sciences disciplines but also significantly dispersed in others such as commerce, and law. Lately, however, women's contribution too is marked by clustering as well as dispersal (Chanana, 2004)

Once women enter higher education at the undergraduate level, they move on the next two levels, namely, the graduate and research level. In other words, their transition from one level to another has increased which highlights their staying power. In 1991-92, 14,79,231 women were enrolled for undergraduate programmes which increased to 3,285,544 in 2002-03; 169,267 women were enrolled for graduate programmes in 1991-92 as compared to 355,893 women in 2002-03; from and 19,894 in 1991-92 to 23,609 in 2002-03 for research programmes. During these years their proportion has also increased from 32.8 percent to 39.9 percent in undergraduate programmes; from 34.7 percent to 42.0 percent in graduate level programmes; and from 37.1 percent to 38.0 percent in the M.Phil and Ph.D. programme. Their proportion is highest at the graduate level while their proportion in research programmes has marginally declined from 39.2 percent in 1995-96 to 38.0 percent in 2002-03. Until 1950-51, only 20.2 women had enrolled for research degrees which increased in the next three decades to 8,780 in 1980-81 (Chanana 1993). Their number nearly doubled to 15,018 in 1988-89. Now it stands at 23,609 in 2002-03. The University Grants Commission has been providing financial assistance to universities for undertaking well-defined projects for research in women's studies and also for the development of curriculum at the scholar and postgraduate levels

and relevant extension activities. The Commission has also created positions of part-time research associate ships for women candidates in Science and Humanities including social Sciences and Engineering and Technology. Research projects related to the theme of women's studies were approved. Also assistance was provided to 21 universities and 11 colleges / university departments for setting up women's studies centre and cells.

The slightly higher percentage at the graduate level indicates that more women are transiting from undergraduate to the next higher level courses. It may also have something to do with the popularity of master's programmes in management, computers and IT, media, advertising, fashion technology etc. which are proffered in the metropolitan cities. But in the absence of statistics, it is difficult to arrive at a conclusion

In fact, there is a general trend of moving away from the general courses to the professional courses which lead to jobs and careers. There is also a big demand for vocational courses at the undergraduate level. As observed in the departments of Management, women seem to prefer human resource management (HRM) and development (HRD) as fields of specializations. It is likely that jobs involving public relations, personnel management, marketing, and advertising in the corporate sector, such as the banks, IT firms, BPO companies are becoming feminine jobs and specializations. It seems that women are moving from discipline choices to specializations within discipline. One could treat post 1991 phase as a period which set forth a change which increased the social demand for specific kind of professional education, especially skill oriented undergraduate degrees which lead to a career and a job. Earlier boys and girls were not expected to work and earn soon after final undergraduate education. Those who did so belonged to the lower middle strata and needed to work and to earn to support the family and themselves. The middle and upper strata, on the other hand, could postpone income generation until further education. This was more applicable to most women across strata, that is, they were not studying in order to earn and to take up jobs. It was an investment in their social status as well as additional criteria for marriage. Although this may still be true of a large majority of women and their parents, that is, they do not expect their daughters to earn after receiving a degree, there are changes in the expectations of parents and of young women in big cities. Therefore, parental expectations and young women's aspirations have been push factors in the shift of disciplinary choices in the mid 90s. It is related to the change in values as mentioned earlier and as a response to market demands in the post liberalization phase. More women are enrolling in engineering and law but the preference for management degrees and computer related degrees and skill is higher. These subjects are available in the fast expanding private sector which responds quickly to the unmet demand for specific skills. Informal debate with key persons reveals that computer applications and software computer engineering as compared to other specializations are popular among women. It will, therefore, have to be seen if women are getting professional training which leads to jobs and careers

There are hardly any micro studies for macro data to fall back upon to answer this question. But as mentioned earlier, there are now differences in the specializations within disciplines which have career implications. For example, HRM requires interaction with the public and there are several others of this kind. In the last few years women have become visible in the call centers; telemarketing; front desk jobs in the multinational/private banks, hospitals, hotels, etc. Quite a few of these jobs are short term and contractual and, therefore, suit the social role expectations of women.

Suggestions for Promoting Women Participation in Higher Education

1. Introduce attractive scholarships for both financially poor students and meritorious students to encourage women students in higher education.

2. Provide counseling for both family and person concerned at the secondary stage of education.
3. Make skill-oriented higher education.
4. Establish non-traditional curricular for women and extend state support for this.
5. Improve transport facilities for women students.
6. Education policy has to be taken to facilitate women participation in higher education
7. Set up more female educational institutions
8. Provide Bank loan facilities for women students.
9. Set up higher educational institutions in rural and tribal areas.
10. Check sexual pestering within and outside institutions..

Conclusion

It must be admitted that women are in no way lesser than men. They have all the power and capacity as that of men. But they fail to manifest themselves for different reasons. In men dominated society they get rare chance to express their voice. In some cases father or husband create obstruction in their path. They even do not allow them to leave the home for higher studies or work. We should have to change our thinking, our attitude towards women. We should have to think that women are not just reproduction. They have feeling, thoughts and all these as the men have. They have all the capacity as that of men and thereby they can do all these as men, if not more. So their power and capacities must be recognized. It is only then women participation in higher education will be enhanced.

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